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Estimation of Litter Production in Mixed Garden Forest Ecosystems

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Abstract

Litter is one of the sources of soil organic matter that develops through the decomposition process, which is overhauled and broken down into smaller particles, producing dissolved nutrients. Therefore, this research aims to determine the litter production from forest land conversion in mixed gardens as a basis for sustainable forest management. The method used is a field survey, in which direct observations were carried out. Subsequently, the types of data collected include primary data by observing the production of litter for two weeks, which comprises the wet weight and dry weight of the litter and the average production of its components, as much as 1 ha. The results showed that Theobroma cacao had the highest litter production in mixed gardens at 1.24 tons/ha/year, while Lansium domesticum had the lowest litter production at 0.06 tons/ha/year, and the most litter contribution comes from the leaves by 60% - 67%.

Keywords: Litter, Mixed Garden, organic matter, forest ecosystem

INTRODUCTION

Organic matter, as a renewable resource, is a source of absorption of plant nutrients (Adamczyk et al, 2019; Zhang et al, 2021), can increase soil infiltration (Adeyemo et al, 2019; Naharuddin et al, 2022) The dynamics of organic matter and nutrient decomposition play an important role in ecosystem stability and the carbon balance of terrestrial ecosystems (Chertov et al, 2001). In forest ecosystems, litter is an important component of the nutrient cycle that regulates the accumulation of soil organic matter (Giweta, 2020).

Litter is directly involved in plant-soil interactions because it helps to introduce carbon and nutrients from plants into the soil (Cuevas and Lugo, 1998). Furthermore, carbon and nutrient cycling are key ecosystem processes driven by the decomposition of plant litter (Chomel et al, 2016; Brovkin et al, 2012).

One of the ecosystems that can store nutrients in biomass, which then transforms into litter and creates humus through the process of humification, is mixed gardens. The quantity and quality of waste determine the functioning of forest ecosystems, which are also important for the balance of the process of the ecosystem (Prayogo et al. 2019). Additionally, litter layers play an important role in maintaining ecosystem productivity, including preventing erosion and maintaining soil structure by providing an opportunity for water to penetrate the surface of the soil (Lakshmi et al, 2020; Soong et al, 2010). Subsequently, litter Mixed gardens generally overgrow as a result of a mix of trees producing stands that frequently shed leaves, flower stems and twigs, and fruit that occasionally falls to the forest floor (Wrede, 2010). The return of nutrients will be significantly impacted when the leaves, branches or twigs of flowers, and fruit in a stand fall. These components of the free substance pole. Litter, which is organic material formed from dead plants or animals that is present above the soil surface, is the term for the waste from these plant parts (Prescott and Vesterdal, 2021; Osman, 2013; Kögel-Knabner, 2002).

Litter is organic material derived from plants and animals that are above the surface of the soil and composed of dead materials. Additionally, its productivity is the amount of litter falling on the ground within a certain period expressed in tons/ha/year or g/m²/year or kg/ha/year. The level of biomass output is known as litter productivity. It differs from a standing crop, which records the biomass from an ecosystem at a certain period. Research of productivity, which addressed the effectiveness of diverse ecosystem types and were also concerned with boosting ecosystem production, were a significant component of ecology.

An in-depth understanding of the main processes (litter production and decomposition rates) in the cycles is essential for sustainable forest management (Giweta, 2020). From a forest ecological point of view, the production of litter is very important in order to return nutrients to the growth of the stand. The lack of research-based knowledge, specifically in mixed garden forest ecosystems, may be a factor in the lack of understanding of the role of plant litter in the forest ecosystem functions for sustainable forest management. Based on this description, research on litter production is crucial in order to establish the basis for sustainable forest management by figuring out the amount of litter produced when forest area is turned into mixed gardens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Time and Place

This research was conducted from March to December 2022 in a mixed garden area resulting from land conversion in Tojo Una-una Regency, Central Sulawesi, as much as 1 ha. Topographically, it consists of 50% plains, 30% hills, and 20% mountains, while the altitude of the area is 105 km above sea level, and the average temperature is 25-30°C.

Research Methods

In this research, the field survey method was used by making direct observations. Additionally, the types of data collected include primary data by observing litter production every two weeks, including the wet and dry weight of litter and the average production of components that make up the litter.

Field orientation was carried out in order to know the characteristics of the field in which the litter trap will be installed and then to identify various types of plants, namely candlenut (*Aleurites Mollucanus*), cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*), and langsung (*Lansium domesticum*).

Litter-Trap Installation

- Create a 100 x 100 m plot in a mixed garden area
- Within the plots measured, tree species were determined randomly for observation of candlenut (*Aleurites Mollucanus*), cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*), and langsung (*Lansium Domesticum*) trees.
- For each selected tree, a litter trap measuring 1 m x 1 m made of the plastic net was installed and placed at a height of 50 cm above the ground. The number of litter traps made was 9 litter.
- Litter data collection was carried out every 2 weeks, and the collected litter was separated according to its parts, namely leaves, twigs, flowers, and fruit.
- The litter collected was then taken to the laboratory to be oven-dried and ended with weighing.

Data Analysis

Estimation of the average litter production was analyzed using the following equation (Aprianis, 2011; Alamsyah et al, 2018):

$$X_j = j \frac{n}{1} \frac{x_i}{n} \text{ (gr/tree)}$$

Where:

X_j : The average litter production for each replication in a certain period

X_i : Litter production for each replication in a certain time period (to $i = 1, 2, 3$)

n : Number of observational litter traps

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics and Conditions of Mixed Gardens

Aleurites Mollucanus, which is about 83.67 cm in diameter and is estimated to be 6–11 years old, *Theobroma cacao*, which is about 27 cm and is estimated to be 5–10 years old, and *Lansium domesticum*, which is about 25.33 cm and is estimated to be 3–7 years old, are the three tree species that make up the mixed gardens. The tree species in mixed gardens are used to support farmers' economic factors.

Mixed Garden Litter Production

The litter production is the loss of vegetative and reproductive structures caused by aging factors, stress from mechanical factors (eg wind), or a combination of both, death and damage to the entire plant by climate (rain and wind) (Aleixo et al, 2019; Martin et al, 2018).

Based on the results of the analysis, the average litter production data per month and per year are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average Litter Production in Mixed Gardens

species	Component composer	Average (gr/phn/month)		average (tons/phn/year)		average (tons/ha/year)	
		Gross weight	Dry weight	Gross weight	Dry weight	Gross weight	Dry weight
<i>Aleurites Molluccanus</i>	Leaf	726,73	540,24	0,00872	0,00648	0,32	0,24
	Twig	330,35	259,71	0,00396	0,00312	0,15	0,12
	Flower	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Fruit	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total		1.057,08	799,95	0,01268	0,00960	0,47	0,36
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Leaf	603,16	428,76	0,00724	0,00515	1,14	0,81
	Twig	55,65	45,65	0,00068	0,00055	0,11	0,09
	Flower	7,71	6,04	0,00009	0,00007	0,01	0,01
	Fruit	222,88	174,12	0,00267	0,00209	0,42	0,33
Total		889,41	654,58	0,01068	0,00786	1,68	1,24
<i>Lansium domesticum</i>	Leaf	620,35	474,66	0,00744	0,00570	0,06	0,04
	Twig	171,95	156,17	0,00206	0,00187	0,02	0,02
	Flower	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Fruit	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total		792,30	630,83	0,00951	0,00757	0,08	0,06

Table 3 shows that out of the three tree species in mixed gardens, *Theobroma cacao* is the most stable species and increases each period with 1.24 tons/ha/year of litter produced. This was due to the species density of 157 trees/ha in *Theobroma cacao* stands. Meanwhile, the lowest species in producing litter is *Lansium domesticum* with 0.06 tons/ha/year. This is because the density of this species only reaches 8 trees/ha. This is in line with the statement of Giweta (2020) that tree density affects litter production. This is also supported by Aryal et al, (2019), stating that the higher the density of trees, the higher the litter production, and vice versa.

According to the elements that make up the litter, leaves contribute the most. In mixed gardens, litter leaves on various tree species account for 60% to 67% of the total. Meanwhile, the reproductive organs (twigs, fruit, and flowers) only contributed about 2% - 33%. According to Mayer et al (2020), increased tree species diversity may have a positive impact on soil C stocks in temperate and subtropical forests, but tree species identity, particularly N-fixing species, appears to have a stronger impact on soil C stocks than tree species diversity. Based on the analysis results, the litter production data based on the components of its composition are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Litter Production in Mixed Gardens by Composition Components

Species	Litter Production (tons/ha/year)							
	Leaf		Twig		Flower		Fruit	
	BB	BK	BB	BK	BB	BK	BB	BK
<i>Aleurites</i>	0,32	0,24	0,15	0,12	-	-	-	-

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<i>Molluccanus</i>								
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	1,14	0,81	0,11	0,09	0,01	0,01	0,42	0,33
<i>Lansium domesticum</i>	0,06	0,04	0,02	0,02	-	-	-	-
Total	1,52	1,09	0,28	0,23	0,01	0,01	0,42	0,33

Description: BB: Wet Weight; BK: Dry Weight

According to direct field observation, about 1.09 tons/ha/year of leaves were produced as litter, as shown in Table 2. This was because leaves were the most abundant component in a single stand tree species in mixed gardens, fruit litter contributed 0.33 tons/ha/year. The composition of twig litter contributed 0.23 tons/ha/year, the lowest producing litter was 0.01 tons/ha/year. However, some tree species in the mixed garden have not yet experienced the season of fruiting and flowering. With high litter that will become organic matter which correlates with richness of plant species, this is in line with the opinion of Tresch et al, (2019) plant species richness positively influences litter decomposition by increasing soil fauna species richness and microbial activity. In addition, land use and soil type affect the contribution of plants and microbial compounds to stabilize organic matter.

According to BMKG data, the amount of rainfall during this research was 6.2 mm, which was considered low. This is in line with the opinion of Wang et al, (2020), which reported that high litter production occurs in the rainy season when rainfall reaches high and wind speed also greatly affects the increase in litter production.

CONCLUSIONS

The highest litter production in mixed gardens from land use change is *Theobroma cacao* species with 1.24 tons/ha/year, while the lowest is *Lansium domesticum* with 0.06 tons/ha/year. The most significant component of the litter, according to the components, is leaves. Furthermore, between 60% and 67% of the trees in mixed gardens had litter leaves, while twigs and reproductive organs only accounted for about 2% - 33%.

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